

A simulation-based, statistical approach for the derivation of concrete scenarios for the release of highly automated driving functions

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Abstract

The technical development of highly automated driving functions (SAE level ≥ 3) has progressed so far that a market launch is anticipated in the short to medium term. The biggest challenge for a fleet approval is the validation and safety proof. Existing approaches such as the statistical, distance-based proof of safety would require billions of test kilometres under representative conditions prior to market launch. This cannot be accomplished by physical testing. Therefore, new methods for the release of highly automated driving functions are currently under development. One of these methods is the so-called scenario-based approach, as proposed by project PEGASUS. It is based on the assumption that a reduction of the test effort is to be expected when exclusively critical scenarios are tested. However, this test effort still exceeds the existing capacity in practice by far. In the scope of the present work, novel approaches for the above-mentioned challenges are investigated, which have the potential to further reduce the parameter space of critical scenarios by using the scenario-based approach. As basis serves a simulation framework, which consists of a coupled traffic and vehicle dynamics simulation. The core of the solution is a statistical evaluation of relevant influence parameters describing a logical scenario in order to derive discretisation stages of these parameters. It is shown that for the application of the Traffic-Jam-Chauffeur, there is a parameter space reduction by a factor 45 for 3-wise and by a factor 30 for 10-wise test coverage in case of the considered functional scenarios. In addition, the potential of a simulation-based determination of occurrence probabilities and value ranges of the influence parameters becomes clear: E.g. for the functional scenario *cut-in*, this manifests itself in form of a time saving factor of 2000 compared to real-world testing.

1 Introduction

In recent years, highly automated driving (HAD), where the continuous execution of the dynamic driving task (DDT) by a human driver is no longer required, has had primarily visionary character. Due to today's growing realisation of various systems of partial automation, a market launch seems to be within reach. With the advent of improved vehicle sensor technology, an increase in the number of electromechanical actuators and the increase in computing power, advanced driver assistance systems can already be provided to the driver with the aim of providing increased safety and increased comfort while driving on the road [1]. For this purpose, a "Vision Zero" for road safety was included in the European Commission's Roadmap to a Single European Transport Area in 2011. The European Union aims to cut the number of road fatalities in half by 2020 and reduce them to near zero by 2050. In this context, driver assistance systems are cited as one of the building blocks for achieving these goals [2].

All subsequent investigations are considering an automated driving function for traffic-jam situations (SAE Level 3 [3]), the so-called Traffic-Jam-Chauffeur (TJC).

1.1 New challenges through L3-Systems

The distribution of responsibilities between the human driver and vehicle systems is subject to change in the case of highly automated driving (SAE Level ≥ 3). For already existing driver assistance systems on the market (SAE Level ≤ 2), the vehicle and its controllability by the driver is in the focus of the validation and safety proof [4].

With the substitution of the performance of the dynamic driving task by the automated driving system for a predefined operational design domain (ODD), a validation and safety proof of the vehicle and the intended functionality of the automated driving function has to be achieved. This leads to the challenge of an increase of both the task quantity and task quality. Hence, existing approaches to the validation and safety proof such as the statistical, distance-based proof of safety would require billions of test kilometres under representative conditions prior to market launch [5].

1.2 Scenario-based Approach

Since the validation and safety proof of highly automated driving functions cannot be accomplished by physical testing, new methods are subject of current research. One of these methods is the so-called scenario-based approach, as proposed by the project PEGASUS [6]. It is based on the assumption that a large proportion of the scenarios occurring in reality on the road are uncritical. Testing these uncritical scenarios therefore does not bring any relevant knowledge gain. Hence, a reduction of the test effort is to be expected when identifying and testing exclusively critical scenarios. However, this test effort still exceeds the existing capacity in practice, e.g. the functional scenario *cut-in* results in a magnitude of $S_N = 8 \cdot 10^{23}$ possible parameter combinations [5]. Within the scope of the present work, approaches are investigated, which have the potential to further reduce the parameter space of scenarios.

2 Related Work

Within the context of parameter space reduction and the systematic derivation of concrete scenarios for the validation and safety proof of HAD functions, important prior work has to be mentioned. As a part of project PEGASUS, a database of relevant traffic scenarios for the validation of HAD functions has been developed [7]. The data sources for the database are divided in virtual data (e.g. traffic simulation data), real data (e.g. field data) and verbal data in form of expert knowledge. By applying a data processing chain containing seven steps, the raw data is transferred to test specification database entities. The data processing chain is based on the frequency distributions of the corresponding influence parameters of a scenario.

In the publication by Olivares et al. [8], a road generator as the first part of a simulation framework is presented. By applying this framework, based on a statistical approach, the derivation of concrete scenarios for the simulation is considered to be possible. As an example, the authors demonstrate a kernel density estimation of the probability density function of the curvature based on highways in Germany's Munich region. Subsequently, Markov chains and Monte Carlo methods are used to sample parameter values and thus derive discretisation stages. The data used is based on OpenStreetMap.

Schuldt [9] evaluated the frequency distribution of curve radius on German highways A1-A9 using OpenStreetMap and mentions the approach of Olivares et al. as a possibility for the derivation of discretisation stages.

Zhao et al. [10] propose the accelerated evaluation concept, which is based on the frequency distributions of the considered influence parameters. These frequency distributions are modified to a so-called accelerated distribution in order to generate more frequent and intense interactions with the object under test. After conducting the accelerated tests, the importance sampling theory is used to skew back the results for the evaluation of the real-world behavior. According to the authors, the approach has the potential to reduce the amount of test kilometres up to a factor of 10^5 .

Amersbach and Winner [5] propose the method of functional decomposition for the reduction of the parameter space. The essence of the method is the assumption that certain influence parameters are only relevant for a part of the functional layers of a HAD function. Accordingly, a reduction of the test effort compared to a system test is achieved through layer-wise testing, the so-called particular tests.

Jesenski et al. [11] propose a 3-circles model as formal approach for describing the important entities necessary for validation of HAD functions. Based on this model the authors discuss which parts of the validation process might be solved by simulations and state possible challenges and limitations. In addition, they summarise and discuss recent research done on the implementation details of simulations for validation, amongst others regarding the modeling of parameter space and test case generation. Based on [12]

they also provide a structure for metrics concerning automated driving. The authors underline the importance of further research on metrics which evaluate the results starting from simulation-based approaches over mixed-reality methods and proving ground tests to real-world driving. Another methodology for a metrics structure is also provided by Hallerbach et al. [13], as shown in **Figure 1**.

3 Methodology

The approach of the present work is based on the method for the simulation-based identification of critical scenarios developed by Hallerbach et al. [13], which is shown schematically in **Figure 1**. For this method, SUMO [14], a simulation package for microscopic traffic simulation is coupled with a vehicle dynamics simulation in IPG CarMaker, using the AXIOM simulation framework [15] developed internally by Opel Automobile GmbH. The virtual prototype of the examined driving function, the so-called object under test, is simulated in AXIOM, which is based on MATLAB/Simulink. The framework is able to evaluate manually defined, concrete scenarios regarding their criticality.

Figure 1 Simulation-based toolchain for the identification of critical scenarios [13]

Within this work, the framework is extended by a methodology for the systematic derivation of logical scenarios. This methodology allows both to define concrete scenarios and to quantify the resulting parameter space and number of possible test cases. First, the potential influence parameters of the functional scenarios within the ODD have to be identified. In the scope of the present work the functional scenarios *cut-in* and *traffic-jam dissolution*, which are shown in **Figure 2**, serve as an example. The characteristic of a level 3 driving function according to SAE J3016 is the presence of a fallback-ready user, who is receptive to take over the performance of the dynamic driving task in a specified latency period. The takeover process prompted by the vehicle is to be regarded as a decisive aspect concerning the controllability of the highly

automated vehicle [16]. In detail, the scenario is designed in such a way that the ego vehicle (Ego) is initially in a traffic jam following the vehicle ahead (Obj 1). Due to decreasing traffic density in the area of Obj 1, it increases its speed. As result, Ego prompts the driver to take over the performance of the DDT as soon as the driving function detects that the system limits will be exhausted within the specified latency period.

Figure 2 Functional scenarios *cut-in* (a) and *traffic-jam dissolution* (b)

3.1 Statistical evaluation of identified influence parameters in SUMO

The starting point of the procedure for the demonstration of the applicability of the methodology, as shown in **Figure 3**, are the identified potential influence parameters of the before defined functional scenarios. The core of the solution is a simulation-based, statistical evaluation of the identified influence parameters. In detail, a traffic simulation is parameterised within SUMO, which aims at mapping a traffic condition that is plausible for the considered driving function. On this basis, it is possible to determine occurrence probabilities and value ranges of the identified influence parameters using exclusively synthetic data.

Figure 3 Procedure to demonstrate the methodology

At this point, the importance of extending the method of Hallerbach et al. by a methodology of a systematic

derivation of concrete scenarios has to be highlighted. In terms of safety argumentation, an extension of the methodology is striven for, which achieves a high degree of compliance with the effectiveness and efficiency criteria for a test concept, as proposed by Wachenfeld and Winner [4]. This is intended to guarantee a resilient overall methodology that e.g. meets the requirements for reproducibility and variability. It should be noted that the statistical approach is based on the fundamental assumption that the probability of occurrence of a scenario correlates with its relevance in terms of the safety argumentation. A plausibility check of the traffic simulation based on macroscopic traffic metrics is considered sufficient for the current implementation, as the demonstration of the applicability of the methodology is paramount. The validation of the resulting occurrence probabilities and value ranges of the identified influence parameters requires further investigations.

3.2 Discretisation of influence parameters

The data generated by the traffic simulation forms the basis for the generation of discretisation functions of the identified influence parameters. Within this process step, the value-continuous influence parameters are converted into discrete parameter values. The starting point of this work is a kernel density estimation of the quantum function of the corresponding influence parameter. With an equidistant increment of the cumulative probability, it is possible to derive non-equidistant discretisation stages for the value range of the corresponding influence parameter, given a number of instances. Ensuring a sufficient number of instances remains an open question: Too coarse discretisation can lead to gaps in the parameter space and thus to potentially undetected errors, while too fine discretisation leads to an unnecessarily high number of test cases [5].

3.3 Functional decomposition

The discretised influence parameters are the starting point for the application of the method of functional decomposition. The essence of the method is the assumption that certain influence parameters are only relevant for a part of the functional layers of a HAD function. Accordingly, a reduction of the test effort compared to a system test is achieved through layer-wise testing, the so-called particular tests [5]. The method is applied to the two considered functional scenarios *cut-in* and *traffic-jam-dissolution* and the resulting parameter space reduction is quantified.

3.4 Deterministic variation of influence parameters

By implementing a deterministic parameter variation, parameter values are specified based on the previously discretised influence parameters, which define a concrete scenario. The sum of all concrete scenarios to be tested is the test suite, which is used in the simulation framework AXIOM [15] to identify critical scenarios. In addition, the

influence of various penetration rates of automated driving systems in the traffic simulation on occurrence probabilities and value ranges of the influence parameters describing a logical scenario is examined.

4 Results

To check the plausibility of the synthetic data generated by the traffic simulation, a comparison is first made with data recorded in real traffic using macroscopic traffic metrics. Assuming that the average speed \bar{v} decreases in a locally homogeneous traffic condition with increasing traffic density ρ (indicating the number of vehicles per unit length), the average flow J in vehicles per time unit can be written as follows

$$J(\rho) = \rho \bar{v}(\rho) \quad (1)$$

The common visualisation of the function $J(\rho)$ is called a fundamental diagram. The analysis of a model using the fundamental diagram can serve as a starting point for further analyses and gives first indications with regard to model plausibility. For small densities, the gradient of the function is e.g. determined by the average speed of the vehicles. For more detailed explanations on the derivation of the function, the reader is referred to the literature [17]. However, regarding future work in this field, special attention should be given to the importance of in-depth analyses of model plausibility. Since the considered application of the TJC is a HAD function focusing on traffic-jam situations, whose ODD is limited to speeds below 60 km/h, traffic conditions in the area of stop-and-go traffic as well as synchronised traffic within the ODD are considered relevant. **Figure 4** shows the traffic conditions obtained from the simulation for the functional scenario *cut-in*, based on an OpenDrive-Map of the motorway junction Frankfurt provided by Atlatec. To obtain the data, the traffic condition of the considered road segment, divided into ten segments, is determined in form of average speed and density. The time interval for determining each data point is three minutes. The traffic flow is governed by equation (1) and the simulation duration is 45 minutes.

Figure 4 Traffic conditions obtained from SUMO

The left-hand area of the figure, up to a traffic density of approximately 20 vehicles per kilometer, is to be assigned as free-flowing traffic. It takes about five minutes passing within the simulation, until a traffic-jam situation develops. For the subsequent statistical evaluation of exemplary influence parameters, therefore, the time span until there is no traffic-jam situation present is filtered from the data record. The data points resulting from the simulation at a density $\rho \geq 20$ veh/km are qualitatively in good agreement with the data observed from real traffic [17]. There are both areas of medium density and medium flows, which can be assigned to the synchronised state, as well as areas of high densities at low flows, which can be assigned to stop-and-go traffic. This impression is strengthened by also considering the average speeds available. While the minimum average velocity detected on a segment for a time interval of three minutes is $\bar{v}_{\text{segment,min}} = 5$ km/h, the analog maximum average velocity has a value of $\bar{v}_{\text{segment,max}} = 43$ km/h. The average speed determined over all time steps and distance segments is $\bar{v}_{\text{total}} = 19$ km/h, which means that the respective values are within the value range defined by the functional specification.

The results show that the developed methodology allows a systematic derivation of logical scenarios and the definition of concrete scenarios. By limiting the value ranges of the identified influence parameters, this leads to a non-quantifiable reduction of the parameter space. As an example, in **Figure 5**, the statistical evaluation of the cut-in distance is represented by a histogram. In addition, the median x_{med} , the standard deviation s , the central quartile distance Q , the coefficient of variation V and the sample size of the dataset N are given. When looking at the data sets of various influence parameters, it is shown that the distributions are visibly different. A prediction of occurrence probabilities and value ranges of the selected influence parameters by expert knowledge seems to be extremely challenging.

Figure 5 Statistical evaluation of the cut-in distance

The discretisation approach is based on the kernel density estimation of the quantum function of the corresponding influence parameter. Built on this foundation, a variable

discretisation can be derived for the range of values of the influence parameter under consideration of a given number of instances v_i . The resulting variable discretisation in the absolute value range of the cut-in distance is shown in **Figure 6** for the case $v_i = 10$.

Figure 6 Exemplary discretisation of the cut-in distance

The dotted lines represent the partitioning of the cumulative probability into equidistant classes. The variable discretisation stages $\delta_{ci,i}$ of the ordinate are illustrated by dashed-dotted lines. The kernel density estimation of the quantum function makes it possible to specify the number of instances v_i and thus to define an arbitrarily fine discretization. The discretisation stages $\delta_{ci,i}$ defined in such a way provide the interval within which the deterministic parameter variation determines one parameter value for the concrete scenarios within the test suite. With reference to **Figure 6**, ten parameter values are defined considering the corresponding intervals of the cut-in distance. To illustrate the different discretisation types obtained, see $\delta_{ci,2} = 0.96$ m and $\delta_{ci,10} = 22.2$ m.

The application of the developed methodology shows that a reduction of the parameter space by a factor of 45 in the case of 3-wise and 30 in the case of 10-wise test coverage is achieved for the addressed functional scenarios *cut-in* and *traffic-jam-dissolution* by the method of functional decomposition. The parameter space reduction as a ratio of the test suite size in case of a system test $S_{t,System}$ compared to the resulting test suite size for particular testing $S_{t,part}$ is shown for various test coverages in **Figure 7**. These results confirm those of the investigations of Amersbach and Winner [5] through the presence of a significant reduction effect. Deviations in the amount of the reduction can be explained, on the one hand, by the number of functional scenarios considered in this work compared to the work of Amersbach and Winner. On the other hand, the definition of the functional scenario *traffic-jam-dissolution*, which is not considered by Amersbach and Winner, leads to a different logical description. This results also in a differing reduction potential over the test coverage. Furthermore, the deviations can be explained by the partly deviating chosen

number of instances v_i of individual influence parameters. It should be noted that with a higher number of considered functional scenarios, a further increase in the reduction effects, depending on the selected test coverage, is to be expected.

Figure 7 Potential of parameter space reduction through functional decomposition

In addition, the potential time and cost savings through the simulation-based determination of occurrence probabilities and value ranges of the influence parameters becomes clear. In the current implementation of the approach, approximately 500 lane changes $N_{lc,sim}$ are evaluated over a distance of $L_{sn} = 3.7$ km. After the emergence of the traffic-jam situation, a real-time factor of approximately $f_{rt} = 4$ is present in the stationary state. The parallelisation factor is currently set conservatively as $f_p = 1$. It should be noted that f_p is limited only by the available hardware. Assuming that on average in real traffic $N_{lc,real} = 0.26$ km⁻¹ lane changes per kilometre are carried out [18], the time saving factor $f_{time,sim}$ can be stated as follows

$$f_{time,sim} = \frac{f_{rt} \cdot f_p \cdot N_{lc,sim}}{N_{lc,real} \cdot L_{sn}} \approx 2000 \quad (2)$$

The calculation is based on the assumption that the time required for pre- and post-processing between real-world testing and simulation is equal. In addition, the advantage of the objective view, or ground truth, of a scene through simulation [19] is pointed out. Moreover, it should be noted that for other functional scenarios an even greater time saving factor can be expected through applying simulation. This is caused by the fact that for the functional scenario *cut-in* only a limited subset of the vehicles on their route experiences the respective lane change within the traffic simulation. By contrast, for the functional scenarios *following* or *traffic-jam dissolution* nearly all vehicles within the simulation experience the respective scenarios.

5 Conclusion

The application of the developed methodology shows that a reduction of the parameter space by a factor of 45 in case of 3-wise and 30 in case of 10-wise test coverage is

achieved by the method of functional decomposition for the considered functional scenarios *cut-in* and *traffic-jam dissolution*. In addition, a systematic derivation of logical scenarios and definition of concrete scenarios is possible. This is associated with a further, non-quantifiable reduction of the parameter space. Furthermore, the potential of simulation-based determination of occurrence probabilities and value ranges of influence parameters becomes clear. This manifests itself for the functional scenario *cut-in* in the form of a time saving factor of 2000 compared to real-world testing, based on conservative assumptions. Moreover, significant changes in the positional and scattering measures of exemplarily considered influence parameters can be observed as a function of the penetration rate of automated driving functions within SUMO. However, the findings of this work are based on different assumptions and only two exemplary functional scenarios were considered. In addition, more in-depth investigations are required regarding plausibility of the models used in the simulation as well as microscopic traffic conditions, which are influenced by dynamic effects on the level of individual vehicles [17]. These factors have a direct influence on occurrence probabilities and value ranges of the influence parameters and thus are to be regarded as particularly relevant for future work on this subject. Moreover, it should be examined whether, in addition to the occurrence probability, other factors, such as the expected severity, are to be used to assess the relevance of a scenario.

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7 Literature

- [1] Pfeffer, Peter: Ausblick - Zukunft der Lenkung im Automobil, in: Pfeffer, Peter; Harrer, Manfred (Hrsg.): Lenkungshandbuch, Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, Wiesbaden, 2013, S. 473
- [2] Europäische Kommission: Fahrplan zu einem einheitlichen europäischen Verkehrsraum, 2011
- [3] SAE International: Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems for On-Road Motor Vehicles, 2018
- [4] Wachenfeld, Walther; Winner, Hermann: The Release of Autonomous Vehicles in: Maurer, Markus et al. (Ed.): Autonomous Driving, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2015, pp. 439-464
- [5] Amersbach, Christian; Winner, Hermann: Functional decomposition — A contribution to overcome the parameter space explosion during validation of highly automated driving, in: Traffic Injury Prevention, volume 20 (1), 2019, pp. 52-57
- [6] Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie: PEGASUS Method, 2019
- [7] Pütz, Andreas; Zlocki, Adrian; Bock, Julian; Eckstein, Lutz: System validation of highly automated vehicles with a database of relevant traffic scenarios, in: 12th ITS European Congress, 2017
- [8] Prialé Olivares, Stephanie; Rebernik, Nikolaus; Eichberger, Arno; Stadlober, Ernst: Virtual Stochastic Testing of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems, in: Schulze, Tim; Müller, Beate; Meyer, Gereon (Ed.): Advanced Microsystems for Automotive Applications, 2015, pp. 25-35
- [9] Schuldt, Fabian: Ein Beitrag für den methodischen Test von automatisierten Fahrfunktionen mit Hilfe von virtuellen Umgebungen, Dissertation Technische Universität Braunschweig, 2017
- [10] Zhao, Ding; Huang, Xianan; Peng, Huei; Lam, Henry; LeBlanc, David J.: Accelerated Evaluation of Automated Vehicles in Car-Following Maneuvers, in: *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 19, no. 3, 2018, pp. 733-744
- [11] Jesenski, Stefan; Stellet, Jan Erik; Branz, Wolfgang; Zöllner, J. Marius: Simulation-Based Methods for Validation of Automated Driving: A Model-Based Analysis and an Overview about Methods for Implementation, 2019 IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC), Auckland, New Zealand, 2019, pp. 1914-1921
- [12] Helmer, T.: Development of a Methodology for the Evaluation of Active Safety using the Example of Preventive Pedestrian Protection, PhD thesis, Technische Universität Berlin, 2014
- [13] Hallerbach, Sven; Xia, Yiqun; Eberle, Ulrich; Koester, Frank: Simulation-Based Identification of Critical Scenarios for Cooperative and Automated Vehicles, in: SAE International Journal of Connected and Automated Vehicles, volume 1 (2), 2018, pp. 93-106
- [14] Lopez, Pablo Alvarez; Behrisch, Michael; Bieker-Walz, Laura; Erdmann, Jakob; Flötteröd, Yun-Pang; Hilbrich, Robert; Lücken, Leonhard; Rummel, Johannes; Wagner, Peter; Wießner, Evamarie: Microscopic Traffic Simulation using SUMO, in: IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC), 2018
- [15] Frerichs, Dirk; Borsdorf, Matthias: Quality for Vehicle System Simulation, in: VDI-Kongress "SIMVEC - Simulation und Erprobung in der Fahrzeugentwicklung", 2018
- [16] Feldhütter, Anna; Gold, Christian; Schneider, Sonja; Bengler, Klaus: How the Duration of Automated Driving Influences Take-Over Performance and Gaze Behavior, in: Schlick, Christopher M. et al. (Ed.): Advances in Ergonomic Design of Systems, Products and Processes, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2017, pp. 309-318
- [17] Krauß, Stefan: Microscopic Modeling of Traffic Flow, PhD thesis, Universität zu Köln, 1998
- [18] National Highway Traffic Safety Administration: A Comprehensive Examination of Naturalistic Lane-Changes, Washington, 2004
- [19] Ulbrich, Simon; Menzel, Till; Reschka, Andreas; Schuldt, Fabian; Maurer, Markus: Defining and Substantiating the Terms Scene, Situation, and Scenario for Automated Driving, in: IEEE 18th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems, 2015